

A Mean-Field Stability Theory for Self-Normalizing Activation Functions

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Abstract. This paper introduces a dynamic mean-field stability framework for analyzing activation functions in deep networks under random initialization. We characterize forward variance dynamics, backward gradient propagation, and curvature-induced feedback through a unified stability theory, reducing stability analysis to a small set of computable expectations. This framework provides principled design criteria for designing and evaluating activation functions that support stable deep signal propagation in large models for big data systems.

Keywords: Mean Field Theory · Dynamical Systems · Signal Propagation · Deep Learning · Deep Isometry

1 Introduction

Deep neural networks rely on architectural and initialization choices that allow signals to propagate across depth without numerical instability. In practice, normalization layers, residual connections, and empirically validated activation functions mitigate exploding or vanishing signals. While effective, these mechanisms often obscure the intrinsic signal dynamics induced by the activation function itself. It therefore remains unclear which aspects of stability arise from the nonlinearity and which are imposed externally.

As architectures grow deeper and more heterogeneous, isolating this distinction becomes increasingly important. Although normalization and residual pathways can compensate for poor conditioning, they do not explain why certain activations behave robustly across settings, nor how to design nonlinearities that remain stable in their absence. This work aims to characterize the intrinsic contribution of activation functions to signal propagation in deep networks.

1.1 Background and Motivation

Classical mean-field analyses focus primarily on variance preservation at initialization. Improper scaling or nonlinearities can cause exponential signal growth or decay, motivating initialization schemes that admit non-degenerate variance

fixed points under random weights. However, the existence of a fixed point alone does not ensure robust depth-wise behavior. In finite-width networks subject to noise and scaling imperfections, stability, therefore, depends on whether perturbations contract or amplify across layers. Thus, beyond fixed-point existence, local dynamical responses of both variance and gradient perturbations are critical.

Existing stabilization strategies address isolated aspects of the problem. Initialization methods such as Xavier and Kaiming aim to preserve variance at depth zero under simplifying assumptions Glorot and Bengio (2010); He et al. (2015), but do not characterize long-range dynamical robustness. Empirically successful nonlinearities were largely adopted without explicit analysis of their induced variance maps or gradient sensitivity across depth. When instability appears, gain tuning, normalization, or residual shortcuts are introduced Ioffe and Szegedy (2015); He et al. (2016); from a signal-propagation perspective, this replaces variance evolution away from the activation itself and into externally imposed workarounds. Although highly effective in practice, when these workarounds are removed, instability often reemerges, revealing that apparent stability may be externally imposed.

While structural workarounds enable successful training, they do not provide a predictive account of (1) the existence of variance fixed points, (2) the stability of those fixed points under perturbation, and (3) the interaction between forward variance dynamics and backward gradient amplification. This paper addresses that gap by jointly analyzing the variance fixed-point structure and the gradient-stability line induced by an activation under mean-field dynamics.

1.2 Theoretical Approaches

Mean-field theory models infinitely wide networks as deterministic dynamical systems governing the evolution of activation statistics (Poole et al., 2016; Schoenholz et al., 2017). A central result is the edge-of-chaos framework, in which scalar quantities characterizes linearized correlation dynamics, and ≈ 1 marks the critical boundary between ordered and chaotic regimes (Schoenholz et al., 2017; Yang and Schoenholz, 2017). Initialization near this boundary improves depth scalability.

However, most analyses study signal propagation by linearizing variance or correlation dynamics around this critical regime. Variance fixed points are typically derived under idealized assumptions and examined using first-order stability criteria. While this explains the existence of critical regimes, it provides limited guidance on robustness away from exact criticality or under accumulated perturbations across depth, particularly when higher-order variance sensitivity or curvature-dependent effects are present.

Moreover, activations are generally analyzed rather than optimized within a coupled dynamical framework. Existing theory compares nonlinearities under criticality conditions but rarely treats activation design as a problem that simultaneously accounts for variance propagation, gradient amplification, and curvature feedback.

We therefore distinguish between correlation criticality and variance-gradient stability. A variance fixed point may satisfy correlation criticality while remaining sensitive to higher-order variance perturbations or curvature-induced feedback. Addressing this requires a dynamical framework that treats variance, gradient gain, and curvature redistribution as a coupled system.

1.3 Contributions

Prior work linearizes correlation dynamics at criticality. We instead analyze the full variance map and its derivatives, derive coupled forward-backward stability conditions, and show that curvature terms structurally constrain activation design. Our activation-centric framework jointly analyzes variance, gradient, and higher-order dynamics as a coupled stability problem.

This gap motivates the present work. Rather than replacing existing methods, we formalize the intrinsic contribution of activation functions to signal propagation through three primary contributions. First, we reframe signal stability as a dynamical mean-field problem rather than a static equilibrium condition. Second, we introduce a stability functional that jointly analyzes variance propagation, gradient gain, and curvature feedback as a coupled system. Third, we apply this framework to common classifications of nonlinearities and constructively derived how simple structural modifications yield robust, quasi-critical signal propagation within self-gated activations without reliance on normalization or architectural intervention.

By extending mean-field analysis to include coupled variance, gradient, and curvature dynamics, we aim to move from static criticality conditions toward a constructive, dynamical theory of activation-induced stability.

2 Mean-Field Stability Theory for Self-Normalizing Activation Functions

This section adopts a mean-field perspective on signal propagation in deep neural networks in order to characterize when an activation function may admit intrinsic stability under random initialization. Rather than focusing exclusively on forward variance preservation or gradient criticality in isolation, we treat stability as a joint property of forward variance dynamics, backward gradient sensitivity, and curvature-induced effects of the activation function.

The central object of study is the activation function viewed as a dynamical operator acting on signal statistics under standard i.i.d. weight initialization. Under the mean-field regime, signal propagation can be described through scalar order parameters governing the evolution of activation variance and gradient magnitudes across depth Schoenholz et al. (2017); Poole et al. (2016); Pennington and Worah (2018).

Within this framework we analyze the forward variance map and the corresponding gradient propagation factor induced by an activation function and

its derivatives. These quantities determine whether perturbations tend to be damped or amplified as depth increases.

The resulting analysis provides conditions suggestive of

1. the existence of a non-degenerate variance fixed point, and
2. the local robustness of that fixed point to perturbations arising from depth, initialization noise, or distributional drift.

These conditions apply broadly across activation families and provide a principled lens for understanding why certain nonlinearities exhibit stable signal propagation while others appear more fragile.

2.1 Network Model

Consider a deep feedforward network with independently initialized weights and no explicit normalization layers. Let $x_l \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the activations at layer l . Forward propagation is defined by

$$z_l = W_l x_l, \quad x_{l+1} = \sigma(z_l),$$

where $\sigma : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is applied elementwise and $W_l \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \frac{g^2}{d})$ with initialization gain g . Bias terms are omitted to isolate the interaction between weight scaling and the activation nonlinearity.

Analysis is conducted in the standard mean-field regime in which network width is large, pre-activations are approximately Gaussian via the Central Limit Theorem, and cross-neuron correlations are negligible (Poole et al., 2016; Schoenholz et al., 2017). Under these assumptions, signal propagation can be described through scalar statistics such as layer variance and expected squared gradients.

2.2 Variance Fixed Point

Mean-field theory reduces forward signal propagation to a scalar variance recursion. Let

$$q_l := \text{Var}(x_l)$$

denote the activation variance at layer l . Under the Gaussian approximation $z_l \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q_l)$, variance propagation is governed by the map

$$q_{l+1} = Q(q_l).$$

Definition 1 (Definition of the forward variance map). *Under the expectation form, the variance propagation map is defined as*

$$Q(q) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma(z)^2].$$

Definition 2 (Variance Fixed Point). *A value $q^* > 0$ is called a variance fixed point if it satisfies*

$$q^* = Q(q^*). \tag{1}$$

Remark 1 (Interpretation). The existence of a positive variance fixed point suggests that, at initialization, forward signal magnitudes neither collapse to zero nor diverge across depth. However, existence alone does not guarantee stability. Additional conditions are required to ensure that q^* is locally attracting and compatible with stable gradient propagation.

This formulation is standard in the mean-field analysis of deep networks Poole et al. (2016); Schoenholz et al. (2017).

Variance Fixed Point A value $q^* > 0$ is called a variance fixed point if

$$q^* = Q(q^*).$$

The existence of such a fixed point indicates that forward signal magnitudes neither collapse nor diverge with increasing depth at initialization. However, existence alone does not ensure dynamical stability, which depends on additional conditions involving the local behavior of the variance map and the associated gradient dynamics Poole et al. (2016); Schoenholz et al. (2017).

2.3 Stable Gradient Propagation

Forward variance preservation does not by itself constrain gradient behavior. Even when activations remain bounded, gradients may decay or explode exponentially across depth.

Let

$$\tilde{q}_l = \mathbb{E}[\delta_l^2]$$

denote the expected squared magnitude of the backpropagated gradient. Under the mean-field independence assumptions, gradient propagation obeys the recursion

$$\tilde{q}_l = g^2 \chi(q_l) \tilde{q}_{l+1}, \tag{2}$$

where

Definition 3 (Definition of the gradient propagation map). *The gradient propagation map is defined as*

$$\chi(q) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma'(z)^2]$$

is the gradient propagation factor Schoenholz et al. (2017); Pennington et al. (2017).

Definition 4 (Gradient criticality condition). *At a variance fixed point q^* , gradient magnitudes remain invariant across layers when $g^2 \chi(q^*) = 1$.*

This condition characterizes the boundary between exponential gradient decay and exponential gradient growth at initialization Schoenholz et al. (2017); Pennington et al. (2017).

Operating exactly at this boundary corresponds to the so-called critical initialization regime, although mildly subcritical regimes may provide greater robustness once higher-order effects or deviations from idealized mean-field assumptions are considered.

2.4 Variance Stability

The existence of a variance fixed point does not guarantee its stability. We analyze stability through perturbation dynamics.

Linearized Stability Analysis

Definition 5 (Variance Perturbation). *Let*

$$\epsilon_l := q_l - q^*$$

denote the deviation from the variance fixed point q^ .*

Expanding the variance map Q around q^* yields the Taylor expansion

$$Q(q^* + \epsilon) = q^* + \epsilon Q'(q^*) + \frac{1}{2}\epsilon^2 Q''(q^*) + \dots$$

For sufficiently small perturbations, the linear term dominates, giving

$$\epsilon_{l+1} \approx Q'(q^*)\epsilon_l.$$

Definition 6 (Local Variance Stability). *The variance fixed point q^* is locally stable if*

$$|Q'(q^*)| < 1. \tag{3}$$

Remark 2. Higher-order terms may influence transient behavior (see Appendix B), but condition (3) provides a first-order stability criterion.

Derivative of the Variance Map Recall the variance propagation map (1)

$$Q(q) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma(z)^2].$$

Differentiating and applying Stein's lemma (under sufficient smoothness assumptions) yields

$$Q'(q) = g^2(\chi(q) + \kappa_Q(q)). \tag{4}$$

Whereas $\chi(q)$ is defined in (3), $\kappa_Q(q)$ is the curvature redistribution term, defined as

Definition 7 (Curvature Redistribution Term). *Define the curvature redistribution term*

$$\kappa_Q(q) := \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma(z)\sigma''(z)].$$

Curvature Control By the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality,

$$|\kappa_Q(q)| \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\sigma(z)^2]} \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\sigma''(z)^2]}.$$

This suggests that controlling the curvature magnitude

$$\xi_Q(q) := \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma''(z)^2] \tag{5}$$

limits the magnitude of the curvature redistribution term $\kappa_Q(q)$. This is favorable considering that cancellation between χ and κ_Q requires infinitely many fine cancellations (Appendix A).

In regimes where $\xi_Q(q)$ is small, the variance derivative satisfies the approximation

$$Q'(q) \approx g^2 \chi(q).$$

Remark 3 (Interpretation). Whereas $\kappa_Q(q)$ denotes the overall impact of curvature on variance stability, be it positive (contracting) or negative (expanding), $\xi_Q(q)$ measures the magnitude of the curvature energy. Thus, limiting $\xi_Q(q)$ limits the magnitude of the curvature redistribution term, not its sign.

Gradient–Variance Interaction At the fixed point,

$$Q'(q^*) = g^2(\chi(q^*) + \kappa_Q(q^*)).$$

Exact gradient criticality corresponds to (4).

Corollary 1 (Tension Between Gradient Preservation and Variance Contraction). *If $\kappa_Q(q^*)$ is small and (4) holds, then*

$$Q'(q^*) \approx 1,$$

placing the system near the boundary of variance stability (3). Thus strict gradient preservation and strong variance contraction cannot generally be achieved simultaneously without curvature effects.

Generally, because $\chi(q)$ directly appears as a functional within $Q'(q)$, gradient preservation and variance stability are intrinsically at odds, and cannot be achieved simultaneously. Consequently, slightly subcritical regimes satisfying

$$g^2 \chi(q^*) < 1 \tag{6}$$

may provide additional robustness by ensuring $|Q'(q^*)| < 1$ with margin. Empirically, stable deep networks often operate in such mildly subcritical regimes.

Curvature control, as measured by $\xi_Q(q)$ in (5), can further reduce the sensitivity of $Q'(q)$ to perturbations, but does not fully eliminate the interaction between forward and backward dynamics.

2.5 Gradient Stability

While gradient criticality ensures preservation of gradient magnitude at a variance fixed point, it does not guarantee robustness to perturbations in the variance itself. Because gradient propagation depends explicitly on q , fluctuations in variance may induce systematic amplification or attenuation of backpropagated signals.

Linearized Stability Analysis Recall the gradient recursion (2),

$$\tilde{q}_l = g^2 \chi(q_l) \tilde{q}_{l+1}.$$

Suppose q^* is a variance fixed point satisfying the gradient criticality condition

$$g^2 \chi(q^*) = 1.$$

Let

$$q_l = q^* + \epsilon_l$$

denote a small variance perturbation at layer l . Expanding χ about q^* yields

$$\chi(q_l) = \chi(q^*) + \epsilon \chi'(q^*) + \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^2 \chi''(q^*) + \frac{1}{6} \epsilon^3 \chi'''(q^*) + \dots$$

Multiplying by g^2 and using gradient criticality (equation 4) gives

$$g^2 \chi(q_l) = 1 + g^2 \epsilon \chi'(q^*) + g^2 \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^2 \chi''(q^*) + g^2 \frac{1}{6} \epsilon^3 \chi'''(q^*) + \dots$$

As in the analysis of $Q'(q^*)$, higher-order terms are asymptotically dominated by the linear term under contraction and therefore do not alter the local stability classification (Appendix C). Consequently, the linear term, and substitute the definition into the gradient recursion formula (2) in order to obtain

$$\tilde{q}_l = (1 + g^2 \epsilon \chi'(q^*)) \tilde{q}_{l+1}. \quad (7)$$

Definition 8 (Local Gradient Stability). *A variance fixed point q^* satisfying $g^2 \chi(q^*) = 1$ is said to be locally gradient-stable if small variance perturbations do not induce systematic exponential growth in \tilde{q}_l through the gradient recursion (7).*

To first order, this requires that the effective amplification factor

$$1 + g^2 \chi'(q^*) \epsilon_l$$

does not reinforce perturbations across depth.

Remark 4 (Role of $\chi'(q^)$).* The sign of $\chi'(q^*)$ determines how gradient amplification shifts under variance drift. If $\chi'(q^*) > 0$, positive variance deviations increase gradient gain, potentially reinforcing instability. If $\chi'(q^*) < 0$, gradient amplification decreases as variance grows, providing a damping mechanism.

Derivative of the Gradient Map Recall the gradient propagation map (equation 3),

$$\chi(q) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma'(z)^2].$$

Differentiating yields

$$\chi'(q) = g^2(\xi_Q(q) + \kappa_\chi(q)) \tag{8}$$

Whereas ξ_Q is defined in (5), κ_χ represents residual curvature effects defined as

Definition 9 (Residual Curvature Term). *Define the residual curvature term*

$$\kappa_\chi(q) := \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma'(z)\sigma'''(z)].$$

Gradient Control Expanding $\kappa_\chi(q)$ through the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality yields

$$|\kappa_\chi(q)| \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\sigma'(z)^2]}\sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\sigma'''(z)^2]}.$$

As in the analysis of $Q'(q^*)$, this also suggests that controlling the curvature magnitude

$$\xi_\chi(q) := \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[\sigma'''(z)^2] \tag{9}$$

limits the magnitude of the curvature redistribution term $\kappa_\chi(q)$, which is preferred due to the fine cancellation issue encountered in the analysis of $Q'(q^*)$ (Appendix A).

Corollary 2 (Gradient Control and Curvature Control). *By minimizing $\xi_Q(q)$ (and thereby minimizing $\xi_\chi(q)$), the curvature correction term $\kappa_Q(q)$ is suppressed, yielding*

$$Q'(q) \approx g^2\chi(q).$$

Moreover, since

$$\chi'(q) = g^2(\xi_\chi(q) + \kappa_\chi(q)),$$

reducing $\xi_\chi(q)$ removes one direct contribution to $\chi'(q)$, leaving its behavior governed primarily by the residual curvature term $\kappa_\chi(q)$.

Coupling Between Forward and Backward Stability Variance perturbations evolve according to

$$\epsilon_{l+1} \approx Q'(q^*)\epsilon_l.$$

Consequently, forward and backward stability are jointly governed by the pair

$$Q'(q^*), \quad \chi'(q^*).$$

Even when $|Q'(q^*)| < 1$ and $g^2\chi(q^*) = 1$, an unfavorable sign of $\chi'(q^*)$ may reduce robustness by amplifying gradient fluctuations induced by residual variance drift.

Thus, complete mean-field stability requires not only variance contraction and gradient criticality, but also controlled variance sensitivity of the gradient factor.

2.6 Mean-field Stability Functional

The preceding quantities can be combined into a single stability functional

$$\Omega(\sigma) = (Q(q^*) - q^*)^2 + \lambda_1(g^2\chi(q^*) - 1)^2 + \lambda_2\xi_Q(q^*) + \lambda_3\xi_\chi(q^*), \quad (10a)$$

which, written explicitly, becomes

$$\Omega(\sigma) = (\mathbb{E}[\sigma(z)^2] - q^*)^2 + \lambda_1(g^2\mathbb{E}[\sigma'(z)^2] - 1)^2 + \lambda_2\mathbb{E}[\sigma''(z)^2] + \lambda_3\mathbb{E}[\sigma'''(z)^2], \quad (10b)$$

with

$$z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2q^*).$$

Because all sensitivity derivatives share a common Gaussian redistribution weighting kernel (Appendix D), stability optimization reduces to shaping the activation's geometry rather than tuning external parameters.

Here $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 > 0$ weight the relative emphasis placed on gradient preservation and curvature control. Rather than defining a single optimal operating point, Ω describes a stability envelope balancing variance preservation, gradient sensitivity, and curvature robustness.

Because analytic minimization is generally intractable, practical optimization over activation families may be performed numerically. The functional reduces the infinite-dimensional search over activation functions to controlling three scalar expectations.

The multipliers λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 act as Lagrange parameters expressing how strongly gradient criticality and curvature suppression are enforced relative to variance preservation. In this sense, they reflect modeling priorities rather than arbitrary hyperparameters.

3 Discussion and Limitation

3.1 Scope and Assumptions

The analysis is conducted at random initialization in the infinite-width limit under standard mean-field assumptions: approximately Gaussian pre-activations, independence across neurons, and a fixed effective gain across layers. Under these conditions, the results provide sufficient criteria for well-conditioned signal propagation in plain feedforward architectures.

Architectural mechanisms such as normalization layers, residual connections, and adaptive scaling optimizers are not modeled explicitly, as these techniques dynamically modify activation statistics during training and may therefore obscure the intrinsic signal-propagation properties of the activation function itself.

3.2 Limitations

The framework isolates conditioning near initialization and does not model late-stage feature learning, finite-width correlations, or generalization effects. Curvature terms quantify higher-order feedback in the variance map rather than Hessian spectra or optimization geometry. Extending the stability functional to architectures with normalization, skip connections, or attention mechanisms remains future work.

Despite these limitations, the analysis establishes that activation stability is fundamentally structural. By expressing forward and backward signal health through coupled moment conditions, the theory provides a principled basis for evaluating and designing nonlinearities for deep, large-scale systems without relying solely on empirical tuning.

4 Conclusion

We introduced a unified mean-field framework for analyzing signal propagation in deep neural networks through coupled variance, gradient, and curvature dynamics. By elevating activation design as a constrained stability problem, we defined a stability functional Ω that compresses the internal conditioning of deep networks into a small set of interpretable distributional quantities. This formulation allows activations to be evaluated and optimized based on intrinsic properties independently of depth, width, or task.

Within this framework, stability appears as a regime: variance dynamics are locally contracting, gradients remain near unity without exact critical tuning, and curvature feedback is bounded rather than delicately canceled. These properties arise from the interaction of variance, gradient gain, and curvature—not from enforcing any single condition in isolation.

Conceptually, the primary contribution is the separation of internal conditioning from downstream task performance. Activations are reframed as structural components shaping optimization geometry, with future gains interpreted as consequences of improved signal propagation rather than heuristic selection.

Although the theory is asymptotic and rests on standard mean-field assumptions, it yields concrete predictions about depth scalability, initialization robustness, and failure modes of common nonlinearities. Empirical results indicate that enforcing activation-level stability improves trainability even outside the strict infinite-width regime.

In summary, stable signal propagation is not an incidental feature of effective activations but a design objective that can be explicitly analyzed and optimized. The proposed framework bridges mean-field theory and practical activation design, providing a principled foundation for scalable deep learning systems.

A Sensitivity-Curvature Cancellation Is Not Robust

Recall that the variance derivative satisfies

$$Q'(q) = g^2(\chi(q) + \kappa_Q(q)),$$

where

$$\chi(q) = \mathbb{E}[\sigma'(z)^2], \quad \kappa_Q(q) = \mathbb{E}[\sigma(z)\sigma''(z)], \quad z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2q).$$

Suppose a variance fixed point q^* satisfies exact cancellation

$$\chi(q^*) + \kappa_Q(q^*) = 0.$$

Let $z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2(q^* + \epsilon))$ denote a small variance perturbation. Because χ and κ_Q are analytic in q for smooth σ , their sum admits the expansion

$$\chi(q^* + \epsilon) + \kappa_Q(q^* + \epsilon) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\epsilon^n}{n!} (\chi^{(n)}(q^*) + \kappa_Q^{(n)}(q^*)).$$

Cancellation at q^* removes only the constant term. Persistence of cancellation in a neighborhood requires

$$\chi^{(n)}(q^*) + \kappa_Q^{(n)}(q^*) = 0 \quad \forall n,$$

which implies $\chi + \kappa_Q \equiv 0$ locally by analyticity.

Therefore exact cancellation at a single variance point is not structurally robust: arbitrarily small perturbations generically modify the first nonzero coefficient and change the local stability classification.

B Higher-Order Derivatives in Variance Dynamics

Variance evolution follows

$$q_{l+1} = Q(q_l),$$

where Q is analytic near a fixed point q^* satisfying $Q(q^*) = q^*$.

Let $\epsilon_l = q_l - q^*$. Taylor expansion gives

$$\epsilon_{l+1} = Q'(q^*)\epsilon_l + O(\epsilon_l^2).$$

By the classical linearization principle for one-dimensional analytic dynamical systems, the fixed point is locally asymptotically stable iff

$$|Q'(q^*)| < 1.$$

Higher-order derivatives contribute only $O(\epsilon^2)$ corrections and therefore do not affect the local stability classification.

C Higher-Order Derivatives in Gradient Dynamics

Gradient propagation obeys

$$\tilde{q}_l = g^2 \chi(q_l) \tilde{q}_{l+1},$$

where $g^2 \chi(q^*) = 1$ at a variance fixed point q^* . Let $\epsilon_l = q_l - q^*$. Expanding χ near q^* yields

$$g^2 \chi(q^* + \epsilon) = 1 + g^2 \chi'(q^*)\epsilon + O(\epsilon^2).$$

Taking logarithms gives

$$\ln \tilde{q}_l = \ln \tilde{q}_{l+1} + g^2 \chi'(q^*)\epsilon_l + O(\epsilon_l^2).$$

If $|Q'(q^*)| < 1$, then $\epsilon_l = O(\rho^l)$ for some $\rho < 1$. Thus $\epsilon_l^2 = o(\epsilon_l)$ and higher-order terms are asymptotically negligible.

Therefore the local stability of gradient dynamics depends only on the first derivative $g^2 \chi'(q^*)$, while higher derivatives influence only transient corrections.

D Gaussian Redistribution Structure of Stability Derivatives

Let

$$\rho_q(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi g^2 q}} e^{-z^2/(2g^2 q)}$$

denote the Gaussian density. For any sufficiently smooth function f ,

$$\frac{d}{dq} \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, g^2 q)}[f(z)] = \int f(z) W(z) dz$$

where

$$W(z) = \left(\frac{z^2}{2g^2 q^2} - \frac{1}{2q} \right) \rho_q(z).$$

Thus all variance derivatives reduce to integrals against the same redistribution kernel $W(z)$, which satisfies

$$\int W(z) dz = 0$$

and changes sign at $|z| = g\sqrt{q}$, implying that increases in variance shift probability mass from the Gaussian core toward the tails.

Consequently, all stability derivatives share a universal structure in which the activation function determines how energy is distributed between the Gaussian core and its tails.

D.1 Interpretation: Core-Tail Redistribution

The kernel $W(z)$ reveals that variance derivatives are determined by a competition between two regions of the Gaussian measure:

$$|z| < g\sqrt{q} \quad (\text{Gaussian core}), \quad |z| > g\sqrt{q} \quad (\text{Gaussian tails}).$$

Because $W(z)$ integrates to zero and changes sign at $|z| = g\sqrt{q}$, increasing variance redistributes probability mass from the Gaussian core toward the tails.

Consequently the sign of any derivative

$$\frac{d}{dq} \mathbb{E}[f(z)]$$

is determined by whether $f(z)$ allocates relatively more energy to the tails or to the central region of the distribution, providing a geometric interpretation of stability derivatives:

- activations concentrated near the origin tend to suppress them.
- activations whose squared magnitude grows rapidly in the tails tend to increase variance derivatives.
- balanced activations produce near cancellation between core and tail contributions.

Thus mean-field stability properties reduce to a geometric property of the activation function: how its magnitude and derivative distribute energy between the Gaussian core and its tails.

Contributions from the central region enter the integral with opposite sign to contributions from the tails. Stability derivatives are therefore determined by how the activation redistributes magnitude between these two regions. Activations whose magnitude grows rapidly in the tails amplify positive contributions from the outer region and tend to increase variance derivatives. Conversely, activations concentrated near the origin emphasize the central region and tend to suppress derivative growth.

Thus far, mean-field stability is governed not only by the scale of the activation but by its geometric distribution relative to the Gaussian measure.

Bibliography

- Xavier Glorot and Yoshua Bengio. Understanding the difficulty of training deep feedforward neural networks. *Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pages 249–256, 2010.
- Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Delving deep into rectifiers: Surpassing human-level performance on imagenet classification. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, pages 1026–1034, 2015.
- Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 770–778, 2016.
- Sergey Ioffe and Christian Szegedy. Batch normalization: Accelerating deep network training by reducing internal covariate shift. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 448–456, 2015.
- Jeffrey Pennington and Pratik Worah. The emergence of spectral universality in deep networks. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2018.
- Jeffrey Pennington, Samuel Schoenholz, and Surya Ganguli. Resurrecting the sigmoid in deep learning through dynamical isometry. *NeurIPS*, 2017.
- Ben Poole, Subhaneil Lahiri, Maithra Raghu, Jascha Sohl-Dickstein, and Surya Ganguli. Exponential expressivity in deep neural networks through transient chaos. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2016.
- Samuel S Schoenholz, Justin Gilmer, Surya Ganguli, and Jascha Sohl-Dickstein. Deep information propagation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1611.01232*, 2017.
- Greg Yang and Samuel S Schoenholz. Mean field residual networks: On the edge of chaos. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30, 2017.